

**Gold nanoparticle-based electrochemical magnetoimmunosensor for rapid
detection of anti-hepatitis B virus antibodies in human serum**

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ABSTRACT

A sandwich immunoassay using magnetic beads as bioreaction platforms and AuNPs as electroactive labels for the electrochemical detection of human IgG antibodies anti-Hepatitis B surface antigen (HBsAg), is here presented as an alternative to the standard methods used in hospitals for the detection of human antibodies directed against HBsAg (such as ELISA or MEIA). The electrochemical detection of AuNPs is carried out approaching their catalytic properties towards the hydrogen evolution in an acidic medium, without previous nanoparticle dissolution. The obtained results are a good promise toward the development of a fully integrated biosensing set-up. The developed technology based on this detection mode would be simple to use, low cost and integrated into a portable instrumentation that may allow its application even at doctor-office. The sample volumes required can be lower than those used in the traditional methods. This may lead to several other applications with interest for clinical control.

KEYWORDS: Hepatitis B; gold nanoparticles; immunosensor; magnetosandwich immunoassay; screen-printed electrodes; hydrogen evolution electrocatalysis.

1. INTRODUCTION

Viral hepatitis due to hepatitis B virus is a major public health problem all over the world. Hepatitis B is a complex virus, which replicates primarily in the liver, causing inflammation and damage, but it can also be found in other infected organs and in lymphocytes. For this reason, the hepatitis B vaccine is strongly recommended for healthcare workers, people who live with someone with hepatitis B, and others at higher risk. In many countries, hepatitis B vaccine is inoculated to all infants and it is also recommended to previously unvaccinated adolescents.

The external surface of this virus is composed of a viral envelope protein also called hepatitis B surface antigen (HBsAg). Previously infected and vaccinated people show normally high levels of IgG antibodies against this antigen (α -HBsAg IgG). The presence or absence of these antibodies in human serum is useful to determine the need for vaccination (if α -HBsAg IgG antibodies are absent), to check the immune response in patients which has suffered hepatitis B, the evolution of chronic HB carrier patients and also the immunity of vaccinated people [McMahon et al., 2005].

Current methods for the detection of α -HBsAg IgG antibodies such as Enzyme-Linked Immunosorbent Assay (ELISA) and Microparticle Enzyme Immunoassay (MEIA) are time-consuming, and require advanced instrumentation. Hence, alternative cost-effective methods that employ simple/user-friendly instrumentation and are able to provide adequate sensitivity and accuracy would be ideal for this kind of analysis. In this context, biosensor technology coupled with the use of nanoparticles (NPs) tags offers benefits compared to traditional methods in terms of time of analysis, sensitivity and simplicity. From the variety of NPs, gold nanoparticles (AuNPs) have gained attention in the last years due to the unique structural, electronic, magnetic, optical, and

catalytic properties which have made them a very attractive material for biosensor systems and bioassays.

Sensitive electrochemical DNA sensors [Pumera et al., 2005; Castañeda et al., 2007; Marín et al., 2009], immunosensors [Ambrosi et al., 2007; De la Escosura-Muñiz et al., 2009a] and other bioassays have recently been developed by our group and others [De la Escosura-Muñiz et al., 2008] using AuNPs or other NPs as labels and providing direct detection without prior chemical dissolution. In some of these bioassays, magnetic beads (MBs) are used as platforms of the bioreactions, providing important advantages: i) the analyte is preconcentrated on the surface of the MBs, ii) applying a magnetic field, the complex MB-analyte can be separated from the matrix of the sample, minimizing matrix effects and improving the selectivity of the assay.

Furthermore, we have recently reported a novel cell sensor based on a new electrotransducing platform (screen-printed carbon electrodes-SPCEs-) where the cells are cultured and then recognized by specific antibodies [Díaz et al., 2009] labeled with AuNPs [De la Escosura-Muñiz et al., 2009b]. These AuNPs are chronoamperometrically detected approaching their catalytic properties on the hydrogen evolution, avoiding their chemical dissolution.

Here we present a novel magnetosandwich assay based on AuNPs tags for the capturing of α -HBsAg IgG antibodies in human sera of patients previously exposure to hepatitis B (either for infection, reinfection or for vaccination) and final chronoamperometric detection approaching the catalytic properties of AuNPs on the hydrogen evolution reaction. The α -HBsAg IgG antibodies concentration in the sera samples has been previously calculated by a standard method (MEIA), finding that the sensitivity of the electrochemical biosensor is high enough so as to detect the HB responders.

2. EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

2.1. Apparatus and electrodes

The electrochemical transducers used were homemade screen-printed carbon electrodes (SPCEs), consisting of three electrodes: working electrode, reference electrode and counter electrode in a single strip fabricated with a semi-automatic screen-printing machine DEK248 (DEK International, Switzerland). The reagents used for this process were: Autostat HT5 polyester sheet (McDermid Autotype, UK) and Electrodag 423SS carbon ink, Electrodag 6037SS silver/silver chloride ink and Minico 7000 Blue insulating ink (Acheson Industries, The Netherlands). (See the detailed SPCE fabrication procedure and pictures of the obtained sensors in the *supplementary material*-Fig. S1-).

The electrochemical experiments were performed with a μ Autolab II (Echo Chemie, The Netherlands) potentiostat/galvanostat connected to a PC and controlled by Autolab GPES software. All measurements were carried out at room temperature, with a working volume of 50 μ L, which was enough to cover the three electrodes contained in the home made Screen-Printed Carbon Electrodes (SPCEs) used as electrotransducers connected to the potentiostat by a home made edge connector module.

A Transmission Electron Microscope (TEM) Jeol JEM-2011 (Jeol Ltd, Japan) was used to characterize the gold nanoparticles and the magnetosandwich complexes.

2.2. Reagents and solutions

Tosylactivated Magnetic Beads (MBs) 2.8 μ m sized were purchased from Dynal Biotech (M-280, Invitrogen, Spain). Recombinant hepatitis B surface Antigen (HBsAg)

subtype adw2 was produced by Shanta Biotechnics Limited (Hyderabad, India) (stock solution 1130 $\mu\text{g/mL}$). Serum samples were obtained from previously HB infected, reinfected or vaccinated patients from Hospital Meixoeiro, Complejo Hospitalario Universitario de Vigo (CHUVI). Goat antibodies directed against human IgG antibodies (αHIgG antibodies), hydrogen tetrachloroaurate (III) trihydrate ($\text{HAuCl}_4 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 99.9%) and trisodium citrate ($\text{Na}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{O}_7 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Spain). Unless otherwise stated, all buffer reagents and other inorganic chemicals were supplied by Sigma, Aldrich or Fluka (Spain). All chemicals were used as received and all aqueous solutions were prepared in double-distilled water. The borate buffer solution (BB) was prepared with 0.1M boric acid and adjusted to pH 9.2 with NaOH 5M. Phosphate buffer solution (PBS) was composed of 0.1M phosphate buffered saline pH 7.4. Blocking buffer solution consisted in a PBS pH 7.4 solution with 0.5% (w/v) bovine serum albumin (BSA). The washing buffer (WB) consisted in PBS, pH 7.4, solution with 0.05% Tween 20. Analytical grade (Merck, Spain) HCl was prepared with ultra-pure water.

2.3. Methods

Preparation and modification of gold nanoparticles

The 20-nm gold nanoparticles (AuNPs) were synthesized by reducing tetrachloroauric acid with trisodium citrate, a method pioneered by Turkevich [Turkevich et al., 1951] (see the experimental procedure for AuNP synthesis and TEM images in the *supplementary material*-Fig. S2-). The conjugation of AuNPs to goat polyclonal antibodies anti-human IgG ($\alpha\text{-HIgG}$) was performed according to the following procedure, previously optimized by our group [Ambrosi et al., 2007]: 1.5 mL of 3 nM

AuNPs colloidal solution was mixed with 100 μL of 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ of antibody solution and incubated at 25 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 20 min. Subsequently, a blocking step with 100 μL of 1 mg/mL BSA, incubating at 25 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 20 min was undertaken. Finally, a centrifugation at 14000 rpm for 20 min was carried out, and AuNPs/ α -HIgG conjugate was reconstituted in PBS-Tween (0.05%) solution.

Magnetosandwich assay using gold nanoparticle labels

The magnetosandwich assay was performed following a methodology previously optimized in our group [De la Escosura-Muñiz et al., 2009a], with some variations. Briefly, 2.5 μL stock solution of washed tosylactivated magnetic beads (MBs) were incubated at 37 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ under gentle stirring, with 12.5 μL HBsAg in BB pH 9.2 solution, during 45 minutes in a TS-100 ThermoShaker. The MB immobilized antigen matrix was then separated from solution by magnetic separation, and resuspended in blocking buffer (PBS-BSA 5%) to block any remaining active surface of MBs. The blocking step was performed at 25 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 60 minutes under gentle stirring. After washing with PBS-tween, incubation with 25 μL of human serum (serum of post infected patients) was performed at 25 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ during 30 minutes under gentle stirring. A non immune serum was used as a control for this assay. The resulting immunocomplex was magnetically separated from serum matrix and washed with PBS-tween and PBS solutions. The last incubation step, with the AuNPs/ α -HIgG conjugate previously prepared, was performed under the same conditions as the last incubation with subsequently washing steps, resulting in the complete magnetoimmunosandwich assay that was ready to be analyzed.

Electrocatalytic detection

Quantitative analyses were carried out taking advantage of the chronoamperometric mode. Chronoamperograms were obtained by placing a mixture of 25 μL of 2 M HCl and 25 μL of the magnetosandwich (performed for sera containing different $\alpha\text{-HBsAg}$ IgG concentrations) solution onto the surface of the electrodes and, subsequently, holding the working electrode at a potential of +1.35 V for 1 min and then applying a negative potential of -1.00 V for 5 min, recording the cathodic current generated. The absolute value of the current registered at 200 seconds was chosen as analytical signal. The background (blank curve) was recorded for a magnetosandwich performed in PBS buffer (without $\alpha\text{-HBsAg}$ IgG), instead of human serum, onto the electrode surface and following the same electrochemical protocol. A new electrode was employed for each measurement. The concentration of $\alpha\text{-HBsAg}$ IgG antibodies in each serum sample was previously evaluated by MEIA using an AxSYM Analyzer System from Abbot Diagnostics (USA). The system was previously calibrated using AxSYM AUSAB (hepatitis B surface antigen; recombinant; subtypes ad and ay) standard calibrators in the range between 0-1000 mIU/mL (concentration standardized against the World Health Organization Reference Standard).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The experimental procedure for capturing the $\alpha\text{-HBsAg}$ IgG antibodies from human sera and the further signaling with AuNPs tags is schematized in **Figure 1**. MBs modified with tosyl groups are used as platforms of the bioreactions, allowing to preconcentrate the sample and also to avoid unspecific adsorptions on the surface of the

electrotransducer. The used MBs can easily be conjugated with molecules that have amino- or carboxi- groups, by nucleophilic substitution reaction. Approaching this property, hepatitis B surface antigens (HBsAg) are immobilized onto the surface of the MBs, ensuring in this way an active surface (MB/HBsAg) for capturing α -HBsAg IgG antibodies, whose unspecific adsorption on the tosylactivated MBs is avoided by a blocking step using BSA. When adding the sera samples, the α -HBsAg IgG analyte recognize the specific antigens forming the MB/HBsAg/ α -HBsAg IgG complex. After a washing step, the α -HBsAg IgG antibodies selectively attached onto MB/HBsAg are captured by goat polyclonal antibodies anti-Human IgG (HIgG) previously conjugated with AuNPs. This secondary immunoreaction gives rise to the formation of the final complex (MB/HBsAg/ α -HBsAg IgG/AuNPs/ α -HIgG), where the quantity of AuNPs is proportional to the concentration of α -HBsAg IgG antibodies in the sample. **Figure 2** shows TEM image of MB/HBsAg/ α -HBsAg IgG/AuNPs/ α -HIgG formed following the reported procedure. AuNPs (small black points) covering the surface of the MBs (big spheres) can be observed demonstrating the specificity of the assay. The results obtained by TEM images were followed by electrochemical measurements. A 25 μ L sample of the magnetosandwich complex placed onto the surface of the SPCE electrotransducer was detected through measuring of the AuNPs catalytic properties on the hydrogen evolution [Chikae et al., 2006; De la Escosura-Muñiz et al., 2009b] at an adequate potential (usually -1.0 V) in an acidic medium. This catalytic effect has also been observed for platinum and palladium nanoparticles [Meier et al., 2004]. Nevertheless the use of AuNPs as here reported are more suitable for biosensing purposes, due to their simple synthesis, narrow size distribution, biocompatibility, and easy bioconjugation. It was also found that a previous oxidation of the AuNPs at +1.35 V was necessary for obtaining the best electrocatalytic effect on the hydrogen evolution in

the further reductive step (data not shown). During the application of this potential, some gold atoms in the outer layers of AuNPs surface are transformed into Au (III) ions. These ions could also exert a catalytic effect on hydrogen evolution [Díaz-González et al., 2008] together with the significant number of AuNPs still remaining after the oxidation step. After that, the catalytic current generated by the reduction of the hydrogen ions is chronoamperometrically recorded and related to the quantity of the α -HBsAg IgG antibodies. The electroreduction potential has been previously optimized (in the range -0.80 V to -1.20 V) and as a compromise between signal intensity and reproducibility a potential value of -1.00 V was found as optimal. In **Figure 3A** are shown the chronoamperograms recorded following the procedure detailed in methods section, for magnetosandwich assays performed in a non immune serum as control (**a**) and for assays performed in sera containing 5 (**b**), 10.1 (**c**), 30.5 (**d**), 69.2 (**e**) and 132 (**f**) mIU/mL of α -HBsAg IgG antibodies. As it can be observed, the cathodic catalytic current increases when increasing the concentration of antibodies in the samples, as it was expected. The curve presented in **Figure 3B** shows that there is a good linear relationship (correlation coefficient of 0.991) between the α -HBsAg IgG antibodies and the absolute value of the current registered at 200 seconds (analytical signal) in the range of 5-69.2 mIU/mL, according to the equation:

$$\text{current } (\mu\text{A}) = 0.265 [\alpha\text{-HBsAg IgG (mIU/mL)}] + 30.27 \quad (n = 3) \quad [1]$$

The limit of detection (calculated as the concentration of α -HBsAg IgG antibodies corresponding to 3 times the standard deviation of the estimate) was 3 mIU/mL. Since it is considered that vaccine responders show ≥ 10 mIU/mL (McMahon et al. 2005) our test is enough to guarantee the detection of those levels. The reproducibility of the method shows a relative standard deviation (RSD) of 5%, obtained for a series of three

repetitive assay reactions for a serum sample containing 10.1 mIU/mL of α -HBsAg IgG antibodies.

Finally, a human serum sample with an unknown concentration of α -HBsAg IgG antibodies was electrochemically analyzed. Following the explained experimental procedure, a value of the analytical signal of $36.8 \pm 1.5 \mu\text{A}$ (n=3) was obtained. From the equation [1], a concentration of $24.6 \pm 5.7 \text{ mIU/mL}$ in the serum sample was estimated. This sample was also analyzed by the MEIA method, obtaining a value of $23.1 \pm 1.6 \text{ mIU/mL}$. These results show a deviation of 6.5% between both methods, being this accuracy good enough to guarantee that the electrochemical method is a valid alternative to check the levels of α -HBsAg IgG antibodies in human serum. This accuracy value was also corroborated performing an approximation to the statistical paired sample T-test (see *supporting information*).

The performance of the developed electrochemical biosensor is similar to the achieved in recently reported biosensors for the detection of α -HBsAg IgG in human sera based on optical [Moreno-Bondi et al., 2006; Qi et al., 2009] or piezoelectric [Lee et al., 2009] measurements in terms of sensitivity and reproducibility of the assays. Although the linear range of the electrochemical biosensor is shorter than the reported in these works (serial dilutions of the samples can solve this drawback) we should consider advantageous characteristics in terms of cost, simplicity and time of analysis that make the presented electrochemical biosensor a promising alternative for future point of care analysis.

4. CONCLUSIONS

A novel magnetosandwich assay based biosensor based on AuNPs labels has been developed and applied for the detection of antibodies anti-hepatitis B surface antigen (α -HBsAg) in human serum. The reported assay takes advantage of the properties of the magnetic beads used as platforms of the immunoreactions and the AuNPs used as electrocatalytic labels. The final detection of these AuNPs tags is performed in a rapid and simple way approaching their catalytic properties towards the hydrogen ions electroreduction in an acidic medium. The developed biosensor allows the detection of 3 mIU of α -HBsAg IgG antibodies in human serum, being sensitive enough to guarantee the detection of up to 10 mIU which is the lower limit for HBs Ag responders. The results were compared with those obtained with the MEIA method, showing a deviation of 6.5 %. From all this, it can be concluded that the reported biosensor is a valid alternative to the standard methods for the detection of α -HBsAg IgG antibodies in human serum, in a more rapid, simple and cheap way.

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FIGURE CAPTIONS

Fig. 1. (A) Scheme of the experimental procedure performed. HBsAg captured on the surface of magnetic beads, incubation with human serum containing α -HBsAg IgG antibodies and recognition with AuNPs conjugated with goat anti-human IgG antibodies. **(B)** Scheme of the electrochemical detection procedure based on the electrocatalytic hydrogen generation.

Fig. 2. TEM images of the MB/HBsAg/ α -HBsAg IgG/AuNPs/ α -HIgG complex formed following the experimental procedure detailed in *section 2* for a serum containing 132 mIU/mL of α -HBsAg IgG **(left)** and detail of the region between two MBs, where the AuNPs (small black points) are observed **(right)**.

Fig. 3. (A) Chronoamperograms recorded in 1M HCl by applying a potential of -1.00 V for 5 min, for a magnetosandwich performed in a non immune control serum (blank curve, **a**) and magnetosandwiches performed for sera containing increasing

concentrations of α -HBsAg IgG antibodies: 5 **(b)**, 10.1 **(c)**, 30.5 **(d)** and 69.2 **(e)** mIU/mL. **(B)** Effect of the α -HBsAg IgG antibodies concentration on the analytical signal.

FIGURE 1

FIGURE 2

FIGURE 3

SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Screen-printed carbon electrodes (SPCEs) fabrication.

The electrochemical transducers used for the in-situ growth of the cells were home made screen-printed carbon electrodes (SPCEs), consisted of three electrodes: working electrode WE, reference electrode RE and counter electrode CE in a single strip. The full size of the sensor strip was 29mm x 6.7mm, and the WE diameter was 3mm. The fabrication of the SPCEs was carried out in three steps. First, a graphite layer is printed onto the polyester sheet, using the screen-printing machine with the stencil (where it is the electron pattern). After curing during 15 minutes at 95°C, a Ag/AgCl layer is printed and cured during 15 minutes at 95°C. Finally, the insulating ink is printed and cured at 95°C for 20 minutes.

Images of the 45 sensors sheet obtained following the detailed experimental procedure are shown in figure S1A.

Gold nanoparticles preparation

200 mL of 0.01% H₂AuCl₄ solution were boiled with vigorous stirring. 5mL of a 1% trisodium citrate solution were added quickly to the boiling solution. When the solution turned deep red, indicating the formation of gold nanoparticles, the solution was left stirring and cooling down. In this way, a dispersed solution of AuNPs 20 nm sized was obtained. Some TEM images of these nanoparticles were shown in figure S2.

Figure S1. (A) 45 sensors sheet obtained following the experimental procedure described in section 2.2 (left) and detail of a SPCE, containing the three electrodes area: reference silver electrode (R), working carbon electrode (W) and carbon counter electrode (C) (right). (B) Experimental set-up for the electrochemical measurements: the 8 SPCEs are connected to the potentiostat. (B) Detail of the 8-wells system containing 8 SPCEs, where the cells are cultured.

Figure S2. TEM images of the dispersed solution of AuNPs 20 nm sized self-synthesized.

Figure S3. (A) Comparative response of HMy2 and PC-3 cells lines against the different antibodies tested. αIgM and αDR antibodies are conjugated with AuNPs. (B) Immunofluorescence analysis by flow cytometry of both HMy2 and PC-3 cells lines. The percentage of the mean of fluorescence intensity is shown.

